

THE ROLE AND MORALITY OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THEIR CHILDREN

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Annotation; this moqola reveals the role of environmental education in the development of preschool children and the strengthening of methods to increase their education and productivity through exercise.

Keywords; preschool age, environmental education, specialty, emoticon, humor, number poems, speech, development, tasks.

Fiction is an impressive tool for the comprehensive education of children, which makes a huge contribution to the development and enrichment of their speech. Fiction, through poetic images, helps the child understand society, life of nature, human feelings and relationships, enriches emotionality.

- Fiction helps to form feelings of humanity in preschool children, such as empathy, kindness, caring for the little ones, parents and older members of the family.

- Children receive aesthetic and moral imagination from works of art.

- * Folk works, which contain subtle humor, numbered poems, jokes, are objective means of pedagogical influence on such qualities as laziness, cowardice, stubbornness, whims, just self-reflection (egoism).

- It is necessary to conduct the acquaintance of children with children's fiction taking into account their age opportunities, the level of speech development and the ability to receive literary works.

- The basis of early children's (1-3 years old) acceptance of works of art is their emotional attitude towards works of art, their ability to advance various tones, react to them, familiar to heroes and care about them.

- The task of the preschool educational institution and the family at this age stage is to develop the foundation for the literary development of children, to form them as future pupils.

"Of adults (educators, parents, et al.) their emotional involvement in the process of reading or narrating a work of art is the most important interpretation of the shshshng, which carries out pedagogical work with children of early age.

- In the process of introducing children of the early age to children's fiction, it is necessary to develop cognitive and speech skills and attitude towards it.

- A child of preschool age (3-5 years old) will have a wide range of opportunities in the field of art, his artistic images, the acquisition of artistic activities. At this age, along with emotional attitude and sensory abilities, artistic thinking also decides.

- The emotional-holistic reception of a work of art by five young people leads to the fact that the child begins to "play" with them, having separated some images and elements of the plot. At this time, he invents it, perfects some plates, weaves his own fairy tales, begins to distinguish literary genres (fairy tales, stories, poems), is able to see some expressive means of language.

* It is necessary to carry out pedagogical work in two directions on the understanding of preschool children with children's fiction. 1-with the organization of the perception of a work of art as a holistic and completed aesthetic object. 2-Creating the necessary conditions for the development of imagination in children in the process of changing certain artistic images and synthesizing several images.

- In the reception and understanding of literary works by preschool adults (5-7 years old), they develop skills to caress and empathize with heroes; restore the chain of events and establish various meaningful connections within the work and between works; see and understand Open motives in the behavior of heroes.

- A contradictory combination of two opposing principles in the

psychological development of preschool older children is their distinctive features: 1-high creative potential, 2 - imitation and striving for normality.

- Interaction of a pre-school adult with a work of art makes it possible to realize its potential for aesthetic, cognitive, social and speech development.

- * Dialogue-preschool should be the leading tool of pedagogical work with older children.

- * Acquaintance with fiction affects the comprehensive development of speech, namely: sound culture, grammatical structure, vocabulary, fluent speech.

1. The importance of children's literature in the comprehensive education of children

2. Introducing children of early age to children's badai literature

3. Introducing children of preschool age to children's fiction

4. Introducing preschool older children to children's fiction

5. The importance of children's fiction in the comprehensive education of children

6. Fiction serves as a powerful, influential weapon of mental, moral and aesthetic education of children, it has a tremendous impact on the development and enrichment of Child speech.

7. In poetic images, fiction reveals and explains the life of society and nature, the world of human feelings and interactions. These patterns vary in their power of influence: in stories, children learn the lustfulness and accuracy of words; in poems, they advance the musicality, tonality of Uzbek speech; folk tales show the clarity and expressiveness of language in front of them, show how rich native speech is in humor, lively and figurative comparisons, expressions.

8. After the children learn to care for the heroes of fiction, they begin to notice the mood of loved ones and people around them. They begin to awaken humanistic feelings-the ability to share someone's pain, do good, resist injustice. This is the foundation on which principalities, honesty, real feelings of citizenship

are brought up. Feelings come before knowledge; whoever did not feel the truth, he did not understand and did not recognize it.

9. People are unique teachers of children. In any works other than folk works, it is difficult to find such an admirable arrangement of sounds that are difficult to pronounce, a surprisingly side-by-side dialing of words that, according to their slang, are barely different from each other. Sloppy jokes, subtle humor, count poems — an effective means of pedagogical influence, laziness, cowardice, stubbornness, whims, only a good "ointment" against such qualities as self-reflection (egoism).

10. A trip to the world of fairy tales develops the imagination of children, their fantasy world, fantasy. Raised in a humanistic spirit based on the best literary examples, children show their fairness in their stories and fairy tales by defending oppressors and the weak, punishing the bad. And of course, children should receive aesthetic, especially moral, visions from the admonition of adults (parents, educators) on the works read, not from answering prepared questions, but precisely from works of art. Excessive exhortation on the work read is great, and often irreparable harm: a work "scattered" with small questions loses all its attractiveness in the eyes of children, as a result of which children's interest in it also disappears. Therefore, it is necessary to fully rely on the educational opportunities of the art mat.

KD.Ushinsky writes; " As long as the child learns his native language, he does not learn only conditional sounds. Perhaps the mother breast of the mother tongue also did not absorb spiritual life and strength. He explains nature to the child in such a way that no other naturalist can afford it, he introduces the character of the people around him, the society in which he lives, his history and aspirations in such a way that no other historian can afford it; He brings the child into folk works, folk poetry in such a way that no other aesthetic is capable of this, finally he gives the child such logical concepts and philosophical views that,

in adbatta, no other philosopher is capable of this"¹. In this statement of the great educator, not only the results of mastering the native language, but also the method of learning it: "1 teacher's language is trusted, which not only teaches a lot, but also teaches on the basis of some kind of immaturable method, which is surprisingly easy." Thus, while helping children to master a particular work of art in their native language, the educator also performs the task of comprehensive upbringing.

Each age stage in the preschool period puts its own speech development tasks. Due to the fact that with increasing age, the level of acceptance of literary works also increases, they are gradually complicated. Children develop the ability to listen to poetry. From this it is necessary that adults know the age possibilities of children.

Taking into account the age characteristics of children, we will consider the issues of introducing them to children's fiction at each age stage.

LIST OF LITERATURE USED

1. Kayumova N. "Preschool pedagogy". Tdpu publisher T.: 2013.
2. Khasanboeva O. U. et al. Pedagogy of preschool education. T.: Knowledge increases. 2012.
3. .He Was Born In Khasanboeva, Kh.J.Djabborova introducing children to nature methodology. T.: Chulpan. 2007.
4. Q Haydarov, S.Nishanova fundamentals of Natural Science and the environment of children- acquaintance with nature. T.: Teacher. 1992.
5. Mirzamahmudovna, Khujanazarova Nargiza. "THE ROLE OF NATIONAL METHODS IN THE DETECTION AND PREVENTION OF NERVOUS DISORDERS IN CHILDREN." INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF

SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630

Impact factor: 7.429 11.11 (2022): 505-507.

6. Hujanazarova, N. "IMPORTANCE OF FAIRY TALES IN MORAL EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN." International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.1 (2022): 6

7. Mirzamahmudovna, Hujanazarova Nargiza. "LOCAL METHODS FOR DETECTING AND PREVENTING NERVE DAMAGE IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN." INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 12.06 (2023): 148-152.

8. Xo'janazarova, Nargiza. "MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA IJTIMOYIY OG 'ISHLARNING OLDINI OLIH VA QAYTA TIKLASH." Talqin va tadqiqotlar 1.25 (2023).

9. Raximovna, Abdullayeva Nigora. "Methodological Possibilities of Increasing Memory Productivity in Primary School Students." Middle European Scientific Bulletin 17 (2021): 297-300.

10. Abdullaeva, Nigora, and Kamola Yuldasheva. "METHODOLOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF INCREASING THE SPECIFICITY OF MEMORIZATION IN CHILDREN OF KIICHIK SCHOOL AGE." International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology 3.5 (2023): 1100-1104